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AN INNOVATIVE APPROACH FOR E-GOVERNMENT TRANSFORMATION

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ABSTRACT

Despite the immeasurable investment in e-government initiatives throughout the world, such initiatives have yet to succeed in fully meeting expectations and desired outcomes. A key objective of this research article is to support the government of the UAE in realizing its vision of e-government transformation. It presents an innovative framework to support e-government implementation, which was developed from a practitioner's perspective and based on learnings from numerous e-government practices around the globe. The framework presents an approach to guide governments worldwide, and UAE in particular, to develop a top down strategy and leverage technology in order realize its long term goal of e-government transformation. The study also outlines the potential role of modern national identity schemes in enabling the transformation of traditional identities into digital identities. The work presented in this study is envisaged to help bridge the gap between policy makers and implementers, by providing greater clarity and reducing misalignment on key elements of e-government transformation. In the hands of leaders that have a strong will to invest in e-government transformation, the work presented in this study is envisaged to become a powerful tool to communicate and coordinate initiatives, and provide a clear visualization of an integrated approach to e-government transformation.

KEYWORDS

e-Government, Transformation, National ID Schemes.

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**CURRENT RESEARCH ON REVERSE AUCTIONS: PART I -
UNDERSTANDING THE NATURE OF REVERSE
AUCTIONS AND THE PRICE AND PROCESS SAVINGS
ASSOCIATED WITH COMPETITIVE BIDDING**

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ABSTRACT

This article serves as the first part of a two-part series that will provide an overview of the reverse auction concept, building on the best research in the field of supply chain management. In this instalment, we examine the growth of reverse auctions in both private and public sector procurement. We then provide a differentiation between the more readily understood forward auction concept and the emerging practice of reverse auctioning. We then examine the two-sides of the reverse auction savings equation, looking at the “first order” savings to be derived from the use of competitive bidding to secure lower purchase prices, as well as the “second order” savings that can be achieved through making the procurement process more efficient.

KEYWORDS

Reverse Auction, Auction, e-Procurement, Acquisition, Supply Chain, Government, Public Sector, Competition, Cost Savings, Process Efficiencies, Purchasing, Procurement Strategy

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CURRENT RESEARCH ON REVERSE AUCTIONS: PART II -IMPLEMENTATION ISSUES ASSOCIATED WITH PUTTING COMPETITIVE BIDDING TO WORK

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ABSTRACT

This article serves as the second part in a two-part series that provides an overview of the reverse auction concept, building on the best research in the field of supply chain management. In this instalment, we look at the concerns involved in making reverse auctions work in practice – the implementation issues. First, we look at when reverse auctions should – and should not – be utilized by a buying organization. We then examine the decision rules that should be used in determining which of the competing suppliers wins the reverse auction. Next, we look at the best research available as to how the use of reverse auctions impacts the buyer-seller relationship. Finally, we examine what is in essence a “make or buy” decision in regards to whether the purchasing organization should run an auction in-house or make use of the services of a third-party “market maker.

KEYWORDS

Reverse Auction, Auction, e-Procurement, Acquisition, Supply Chain, Government, Public Sector, Private Sector, Competition, Buyer-seller Relationships, Market Maker, Purchasing, Procurement Strategy.

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